

**THE IMPORTANCE OF USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN
TEACHING ENGLISH.**

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Annotation: This article shows that authentic materials are considered to be an essential component in language learning/teaching at all levels also, it is well known by most of experts , it is a an emotive and a debated notion.

Key words: authentic materials, newspaper, video

As ESL teachers, we have many helpful resources to aid our classroom teaching. And we're lucky we can take advantage of technology to find excellent ESL teaching tools online. But a great teacher will also recognize the limitations of ESL materials and introduce authentic resources to expose students to English in the real world. Here are some great ideas to integrate authentic materials in English into your classroom.

1. Weather Report: There Is a Blizzard on the Way!

Familiarize your students with the U.S. climate by exposing them to weather reports. While you can definitely search for "weather reports" on Google, Weather.com is the perfect place to go.

The site features a wide range of weather reports as well as interesting aftermath disaster analyses. Want to know what happened to the MS World Discover Cruise ship after it was wrecked in 2000? Weather.com will tell you!

Another great feature of this site is that, aside from short weather write-ups, it also provides mini-clips to brush up your students' listening comprehension.

You can read a weather report or watch a video from Weather.com in class. Feel free to ask your students to do further research on the subject and make a mini-lesson/presentation that:

- summarizes key points in the weather report
- teaches 2-3 vocabulary related to current weather conditions
- gives practical tips on how to prepare for this kind of catastrophe

Is there a blizzard on the way? Your students can tell you all about it!

2. Menus: Order Your Favorite Dish

Introduce your students to some of the most common dishes in America so they can order their meals with confidence.

Many restaurants have online menus so you can easily download them without driving around the neighborhood. You can also make this exercise easier with popular food-ordering apps like Grubhub and Doordash. Do try to use local restaurants, though, as this will make it more meaningful for your students.

3. Job Opening: 1-2-3 I Need a Job!

Give your students the full experience of job hunting by directing them to sites like Indeed.com, CareerBuilder.com and Monster.com.

On Indeed, for example, all they have to do is to fill out the “Job Title” and “Location” boxes and Indeed will generate a list of matching jobs. Have your students look through the job descriptions and bring three of them to class for discussion.

Form a small group and have each person present his/her job search process. Some questions you can ask your students include:

- What keywords did you use to find the jobs you really want?
- What is the job and what are your duties?
- Why did you pick this job? Discuss your decision-making process to help other students to find their dream jobs too.

Job Application

Because many companies use online application forms to screen their candidates, you can have a class lesson set aside to have students fill these out.

Using the sites mentioned above, have students fill out basic information about themselves, upload a resume or submit a profile photo. You can go through the profile and discuss essential points related to them or have them actually send out those applications and see what happens!

4. Written News: Fact or Fiction

This exercise provides the perfect opportunity to challenge students’ critical thinking skills. Specifically, students will learn how to evaluate the validity of a report and read between the lines.

5. Radio: Listen and Learn

You may want to track down some English radio programs for use in the classroom. For example, the VOA Learning English Podcast has tons of materials on a variety of topics designed for beginner and intermediate English learners.

This exercise is pretty straightforward: Ask your students to listen to the audio materials and give them a list of questions to test their comprehension.

6. Comics: Tell a Story Through Pictures

Beginners may not be ready to be fully immersed in long fictional materials like books and novels. However, you can give them comics instead. You can study

these short fictional scenes with students or ask them to imitate via their own comic strips produced in class for a fun activity.

7. Films: Sit Back, Relax and Review

Beginners can also be shown short films, particularly films for children and animated features (e.g. Disney films). To make it easier to use authentic films English learners can watch, use a language-learning platform like FluentU.

Remember to choose material that is linguistically appropriate. Before handing out authentic materials, make sure you read through them to plan lessons and in-class activities that will reinforce a known idea, teach a new word or explain a complex concept. Authentic materials bridge the gap between classroom language use and real life language use by bringing familiar linguistic situations and materials right into the classroom. When teachers use authentic materials, they are in fact helping ESL students to make a comfortable transition into the L2 culture. Give your students some weather reports and ask them to apply for a few jobs on the web to make learning a part of their everyday life. Your students will appreciate the lessons and remember new words much better when they need to use them for survival. Give your students authentic materials in English. Ask them to look over weather reports or apply for a few jobs on the web to make learning a part of their everyday life. Your students will appreciate the lessons and remember new words much better when they need to use them the way they should be used. As can be seen, using authentic materials is a relatively easy and convenient way of improving not only your students' general skills, but also their confidence in a real situation. This is only a brief introduction to the ideas involved, but some of these ideas could easily be expanded to form part of a motivating and effective course

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